

KERNEL SUBSPACE-BASED ANOMALY DETECTION FOR HYPERSPECTRAL IMAGERY

Nasser M. Nasrabadi

US Army Research Laboratory, 2800 Powder Mill Rd., Adelphi, MD 20783

ABSTRACT

This paper provides a performance comparison of various linear and nonlinear subspace-based anomaly detectors. Three different techniques, Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Fisher Linear Discriminant (FLD) Analysis, and the Eigenspace Separation Transform (EST), are used to generate the linear projection subspaces. Each of these three linear methods is then extended to its corresponding nonlinear *kernel* version. The well-known Reed-Xiaoli (RX) anomaly detector and its kernel version (kernel RX) are also implemented. Comparisons between all linear and non-linear anomaly detectors are made using receiver operating characteristics (ROC) curves for several hyperspectral imagery.

Index Terms— Anomaly detection, kernel machine learning

1. INTRODUCTION

Anomaly detectors [1] are pattern recognition schemes that are used to detect objects of interest. Almost all anomaly detectors attempt to locate anything that looks different either spatially or spectrally from its surroundings. In spectral anomaly detection algorithms, pixels (materials) that have a significantly different spectral signature from their neighboring background clutter pixels are identified as spectral anomalies. One way of designing an anomaly detector is by projecting the input spectra onto a subspace whose bases are generated by PCA, FLD, EST or their nonlinear kernel versions.

A linear anomaly detector is not always sufficient, because real-world data do not fit the Gaussian distribution assumption made by linear anomaly detectors (i.e., RX algorithm [2]). However, by utilizing a nonlinear mapping to transform each spectrum into a high-dimensional feature space we can potentially exploit higher order correlation between the spectral bands. The resulting linear hyperplane which separates the anomalies from the background in the high-dimensional feature space corresponds to a nonlinear boundary in the original input space. Unfortunately, it is not computationally feasible to carry out any algorithms in this high dimensional feature space. This problem, however can be circumvented by reformulating the problem into dot product form in order to use a common machine learning technique known as *kernelization* [3].

2. LINEAR SUBSPACE-BASED ANOMALY DETECTION

One common method used in many anomaly detection algorithms is the dual-window approach. Two concentric windows (dual window) centered at each test pixel are opened creating two disjoint regions- an inner-window region (IWR) and an outer-window region (OWR). The size of the inner window is generally set so that the inner window can fully enclose a target. In subspace-based anomaly detection techniques, projection (basis) vectors are generated using the statistical properties of the IWR and OWR covariance matrices.

Denote a spectral vector within the IWR of a dual window centered at a test pixel by $\mathbf{x}_k = (x_k(1), x_k(2), \dots, x_k(J))^T$ where J refers to the number of spectral bands and $k = 1, \dots, N_{in}$. Assuming that there are a total of N_{in} pixels in the IWR, the matrix $\mathbf{X} = [\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{N_{in}}]$ is of size $J \times N_{in}$ and contains the spectra of each one of these samples as one of its N_{in} columns. Similarly, let a spectral vector within the OWR of the same dual window be denoted by \mathbf{y}_l where $l = 1, \dots, N_{out}$. Given that there are N_{out} pixels in the OWR, the $J \times N_{out}$ matrix $\mathbf{Y} = [\mathbf{y}_1, \mathbf{y}_2, \dots, \mathbf{y}_{N_{out}}]$ is one whose columns are the spectral vectors of the pixels in the OWR representing the background clutter samples.

The projection separation statistic for an input test pixel, \mathbf{r} , is calculated using

$$s' = (\mathbf{r} - \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_Y)^T \mathbf{W} \mathbf{W}^T (\mathbf{r} - \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_Y), \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{W} = [\mathbf{w}_1 \mathbf{w}_2 \dots \mathbf{w}_m]$ is a matrix whose columns are m projection vectors, and $\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_Y$ represent the mean of the OWR spectra. The product $\mathbf{W} \mathbf{W}^T$ is known as a projection operator and represents a subspace characterizing the spectral region represented by the projection vectors \mathbf{w}_i . A anomaly is detected if the projection separation, s' , is greater than some threshold, η . It is also possible to project the difference $(\mathbf{r} - \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_Y)$ onto the complement subspace $(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{W} \mathbf{W}^T)$ given by

$$s'' = (\mathbf{r} - \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_Y)^T (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{W} \mathbf{W}^T) (\mathbf{r} - \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_Y). \quad (2)$$

In the following subsections three different methods are used to generate the projection matrix, \mathbf{W} , in order to obtain the projection operator in the Eqs. (1) or (2).

2.1. Principal component analysis

In order to generate the PCA projection matrix, \mathbf{W}_{PCA} , the OWR covariance matrix using centered data $\hat{\mathbf{Y}}$, $\mathbf{C}_Y =$

$1/N_{out}(\hat{\mathbf{Y}})(\hat{\mathbf{Y}})^T$, is written in terms of its eigenvectors \mathbf{V} and their corresponding eigenvalues Λ as $\mathbf{C}_Y = \mathbf{V}\Lambda\mathbf{V}^T$ the first m eigenvectors $\mathbf{W}_{PCA} = [\mathbf{v}_1, \mathbf{v}_2, \dots, \mathbf{v}_m]$ with the highest corresponding eigenvalues form the desired projection vectors. Using \mathbf{W}_{PCA} as the projection matrix and substituting this result into (1) or (2) we obtain the corresponding projections of the input onto the PCA-based subspace.

2.2. Fisher linear discriminant analysis

PCA does not exploit the information in the IWR and OWR at the same time. However, the FLD analysis attempts to seek an optimal direction for discriminating between IWR and OWR data samples. In order to calculate the optimal Fisher discrimination direction, \mathbf{w}^* , the criterion function

$$\mathbf{w}^* = \max_{\mathbf{w}} J(\mathbf{w}) = \frac{|\mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{S}_B \mathbf{w}|}{|\mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{S}_W \mathbf{w}|}, \quad (3)$$

needs to be maximized over all possible \mathbf{w} where $\mathbf{S}_B = (\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_X - \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_Y)(\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_X - \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_Y)^T$ is the between-class scatter matrix and $\mathbf{S}_W = \mathbf{C}_X + \mathbf{C}_Y$ is the within-class scatter matrix. The solution of (3) is given as $\mathbf{w}_{FD} = \mathbf{w}^* = \mathbf{S}_W^{-1}(\boldsymbol{\mu}_X - \boldsymbol{\mu}_Y)$. Using \mathbf{w}_{FD} as the projection vector and substituting this result into (1) gives the Fischer subspace detector.

2.3. Eigenspace separation transform

In the EST algorithm [4] we first compute the $J \times J$ Difference Correlation (DCOR) matrix $\hat{\mathbf{R}} = \mathbf{R}_X - \mathbf{R}_Y$ which is simply the difference of the correlation matrices of the IWR (\mathbf{R}_X) and OWR (\mathbf{R}_Y) which represents the second order statistic differences between the two regions. The eigenvalue decomposition of DCOR can be written in block-matrix form in terms of its positive and negative eigenvalues and eigenvectors as

$$\hat{\mathbf{R}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{V}_+ & \mathbf{V}_- \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Lambda_+ & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \Lambda_- \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{V}_+^T \\ \mathbf{V}_-^T \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

where the columns of \mathbf{V}_+ and \mathbf{V}_- are the eigenvectors with their corresponding non-zero positive (Λ_+) and negative (Λ_-) eigenvalues, respectively. The matrix $\mathbf{W}_{EST} = [\mathbf{v}_1, \mathbf{v}_2, \dots, \mathbf{v}_m]$ is then chosen to be the set of m positive or negative eigenvectors associated with $\hat{\mathbf{R}}$. Using \mathbf{w}_{EST} as the projection vector and substituting this result into (1) gives the EST subspace detector. The choice of which set to use hinges on which set of eigenvalues (positive or negative) has the largest absolute sum.

3. KERNEL LEARNING THEORY

Suppose the input data set lies in the data space ($\chi \subset \mathfrak{R}^J$) and let \mathcal{F} be a feature space (also known as a Hilbert space) associated with χ by some nonlinear mapping function $\Phi(\mathbf{x})$ where \mathbf{x} is an input vector ($\mathbf{x} \in \chi$) which is mapped into a much higher dimensional feature space. The most significant benefit of mapping the data using Φ into \mathcal{F} is that it is possible to define a similarity measure using the dot product in \mathcal{F} in terms of a

function of the corresponding data in the input space. Thus, it is possible to write

$$k(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j) = \langle \Phi(\mathbf{x}_i), \Phi(\mathbf{x}_j) \rangle. \quad (5)$$

Eq. (5), which is commonly referred to in machine learning literature as the *kernel trick* [3], states that all dot products in \mathcal{F} (a task which is otherwise computationally infeasible) can be implicitly computed by simply using a *Mercer* kernel function k [3] defined in terms of the input data. In this paper, we use a Gaussian Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernel which takes the form $k(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \exp[-\|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{y}\|^2/2\sigma^2]$ where $\sigma > 0$ is a critical kernel parameter representing the width of the Gaussian kernel.

4. KERNEL SUBSPACE-BASED ANOMALY DETECTION

Using a nonlinear mapping Φ , the original data, \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{Y} , in the input space are mapped into the feature space \mathcal{F} denoted by \mathbf{X}_Φ and \mathbf{Y}_Φ , respectively. This means that \mathbf{X}_Φ represent the mapped IWR spectra and \mathbf{Y}_Φ represents the mapped OWR spectra. The statistical means of the mapped data in \mathcal{F} are represented by $\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{X_\Phi}$ and $\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{Y_\Phi}$, respectively. For many of the following methods, it is assumed that the mapped data is centered in \mathcal{F} . Thus, denote each centered vector for the IWR in \mathcal{F} as $\Phi_c(\mathbf{x}_i) = \Phi(\mathbf{x}_i) - \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{X_\Phi}$, $i = 1, \dots, N_{in}$ and similarly for the OWR spectra (i.e. $\Phi_c(\mathbf{y}_j) = \Phi(\mathbf{y}_j) - \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{Y_\Phi}$, $j = 1, \dots, N_{out}$). Then, let \mathbf{X}_{c_Φ} and \mathbf{Y}_{c_Φ} be matrices whose columns are the centered IWR and OWR in the feature space, respectively. Also, let \mathbf{C}_{X_Φ} and \mathbf{C}_{Y_Φ} be the covariance matrices of the centered spectra in the feature space.

The projection of the mapped test pixel spectra $\Phi(\mathbf{r})$ onto a linear subspace in the feature space which is equivalent to a nonlinear subspace in the original input domain is given by

$$s'_\Phi = (\Phi(\mathbf{r}) - \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{Y_\Phi})^T \mathbf{W}_\Phi \mathbf{W}_\Phi^T (\Phi(\mathbf{r}) - \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{Y_\Phi}), \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{W}_\Phi = [\mathbf{w}_\Phi^1 \mathbf{w}_\Phi^1 \dots \mathbf{w}_\Phi^m]$ is a matrix whose columns are the set of m projection vectors in \mathcal{F} . Similarly, projection onto the complement subspace is given by

$$s''_\Phi = (\Phi(\mathbf{r}) - \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{Y_\Phi})^T (\mathbf{I}_\Phi - \mathbf{W}_\Phi \mathbf{W}_\Phi^T) (\Phi(\mathbf{r}) - \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{Y_\Phi}). \quad (7)$$

The following subsections outline three nonlinear kernel subspace methods (kernel PCA, Kernel FLD and Kernel EST) that can provide the projection matrix $\mathbf{W}_\Phi = [\mathbf{w}_\Phi^1 \mathbf{w}_\Phi^1 \dots \mathbf{w}_\Phi^m]$ in order to perform nonlinear anomaly detection.

4.1. Kernel principal component analysis

To find the PCA eigenvectors in the feature space we have to perform eigenvalues and eigenvectors decomposition of \mathbf{C}_{Y_Φ} in \mathcal{F} by solving $\mathbf{C}_{Y_\Phi} = \mathbf{V}_\Phi \Lambda_\Phi \mathbf{V}_\Phi^T$, where Λ_Φ and $\mathbf{V}_\Phi = [\mathbf{v}_\Phi^1 \mathbf{v}_\Phi^2 \dots \mathbf{v}_\Phi^p]$ contain only the p nonzero eigenvalues and corresponding eigenvectors of \mathbf{C}_{Y_Φ} . All eigenvectors in the feature space lie in the span of the vectors in \mathbf{Y}_{c_Φ} . Therefore, they can be represented as $\mathbf{V}_\Phi = \Lambda_\Phi^{-1/2} \mathbf{Y}_{c_\Phi} \mathbf{A}$, where

$\mathbf{A} = [\alpha_1 \alpha_2 \cdots \alpha_{N_{out}}]$ as shown in [3] is a matrix whose columns are the nonzero eigenvectors of the centered Gram (kernel) matrix $\mathbf{K}_c = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{\Lambda}_\Phi\mathbf{A}^T$ and $\mathbf{\Lambda}_\Phi$ contains the associated nonzero eigenvalues.

Utilizing only the m most significant eigenvectors $\tilde{\mathbf{V}}_\Phi = \mathbf{Y}_{c_\Phi}\tilde{\mathbf{A}}_{KPCA}$, where $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}_{KPCA} = [\tilde{\alpha}_1 \tilde{\alpha}_2 \cdots \tilde{\alpha}_m]$ are the m most significant eigenvectors of \mathbf{K}_c normalized by the square roots of their respective eigenvalues, as the projection vectors in (6) and simplifying in terms of kernel function we obtain

$$\text{KPCA}(\mathbf{r}) = (\mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{Y}_r}^T - \mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{Y}_{\hat{\mu}}^T}^T)^T \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_{KPCA} \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_{KPCA}^T (\mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{Y}_r}^T - \mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{Y}_{\hat{\mu}}^T}^T), \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{Y}_r}^T = \Phi(\mathbf{r})^T \mathbf{Y}_{c_\Phi}$ and $\mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{Y}_{\hat{\mu}}^T}^T = \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{\mathbf{Y}_\Phi}^T \mathbf{Y}_{c_\Phi}$; are commonly referred to as empirical kernel expansions [3].

4.2. Kernel Fisher discriminant analysis

The FLD in the feature space is equivalent to maximizing the cost function given by

$$\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{w}_\Phi) = \frac{|\mathbf{w}_\Phi^T \mathbf{S}_B^\Phi \mathbf{w}_\Phi|}{|\mathbf{w}_\Phi^T \mathbf{S}_W^\Phi \mathbf{w}_\Phi|}, \quad (9)$$

where \mathbf{w}_Φ is the projection vector, $\mathbf{S}_W^\Phi = \mathbf{C}_{X_\Phi} + \mathbf{C}_{Y_\Phi}$ and $\mathbf{S}_B^\Phi = (\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{X_\Phi} - \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{Y_\Phi})(\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{X_\Phi} - \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{Y_\Phi})^T$ are the within-class and between-class scatter matrices, respectively, in \mathcal{F} .

It has been shown in [3] that maximizing the Fisher's discriminant (9) in \mathcal{F} is equivalent to maximizing a dual representation given by

$$\mathbf{J}(\boldsymbol{\alpha}) = \frac{\boldsymbol{\alpha}^T \mathbf{A} \boldsymbol{\alpha}}{\boldsymbol{\alpha}^T \mathbf{B} \boldsymbol{\alpha}}, \quad (10)$$

where $\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{K}_{in}(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{1}_{N_{in}})\mathbf{K}_{in}^T + \mathbf{K}_{out}(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{1}_{N_{out}})\mathbf{K}_{out}^T$, $\mathbf{A} = (\mathbf{M}_{in} - \mathbf{M}_{out})(\mathbf{M}_{in} - \mathbf{M}_{out})^T$, $(\mathbf{M}_{in})_j = \frac{1}{N_{in}} \sum_{l=1}^{N_{in}} k(\mathbf{x}_j, \mathbf{x}_l)$, $(\mathbf{M}_{out})_j = \frac{1}{N_{out}} \sum_{l=1}^{N_{out}} k(\mathbf{y}_j, \mathbf{y}_l)$ and \mathbf{I} is the identity matrix. \mathbf{K}_{in} is an $N_t \times N_{in}$ Gram matrix, \mathbf{K}_{out} is also an $N_t \times N_{out}$ Gram matrix, $\mathbf{1}_{N_{in}}$ and $\mathbf{1}_{N_{out}}$ are matrices with each entry equal to $1/N_{in}$ and $1/N_{out}$, respectively. Each element of \mathbf{K}_{in} and \mathbf{K}_{out} are defined to be $(\mathbf{K}_{in})_{mn} = k(\mathbf{x}_n, \mathbf{x}_m)$ and $(\mathbf{K}_{out})_{mn} = k(\mathbf{y}_n, \mathbf{y}_m)$, respectively. The kernel FLD subspace detection can now be written as

$$\text{KFD}(\mathbf{r}) = (\Phi(\mathbf{r}) - \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{\mathbf{Y}_\Phi})^T \mathbf{Z}_\Phi \boldsymbol{\alpha}_{KFD} \boldsymbol{\alpha}_{KFD}^T \mathbf{Z}_\Phi^T (\Phi(\mathbf{r}) - \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{\mathbf{Y}_\Phi}), \quad (11)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\alpha}_{KFD}$ are the leading eigenvectors of $\mathbf{B}^{-1}\mathbf{A}$ and $\mathbf{w}_\Phi = \mathbf{Z}_\Phi \boldsymbol{\alpha}_{KFD}$. We can simplify (11) in terms of kernel function as

$$\text{KFD}(\mathbf{r}) = \left(\mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{Z}_r}^T - \mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{Z}_\mu}^T \right)^T \boldsymbol{\alpha}_{KFD} \boldsymbol{\alpha}_{KFD}^T \left(\mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{Z}_r}^T - \mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{Z}_\mu}^T \right), \quad (12)$$

where $\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{\mathbf{Y}_\Phi}^T \mathbf{Z}_\Phi = \frac{1}{N_{out}} \sum_{\mathbf{y} \in \text{OWR}} \mathbf{k}(\mathbf{Z}, \mathbf{y})^T = \mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{Z}_\mu}$ and $\Phi(\mathbf{r})^T \mathbf{Z}_\Phi = \mathbf{k}(\mathbf{Z}, \mathbf{r})^T = \mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{Z}_r}$.

4.3. Kernel eigenspace separation transform

The DCOR in the feature space can be written as $\mathbf{R}_\Phi = \mathbf{R}_{X_\Phi} - \mathbf{R}_{Y_\Phi}$ where $\mathbf{R}_{X_\Phi} = \Phi(\mathbf{X})\Phi(\mathbf{X})^T/N_{in}$ and $\mathbf{R}_{Y_\Phi} =$

$\Phi(\mathbf{Y})\Phi(\mathbf{Y})^T/N_{out}$ are the correlation matrices in the feature space for IWR and OWR, respectively. In order to diagonalize \mathbf{R}_Φ we must find all the eigenvectors $\mathbf{V}_\Phi = [\mathbf{V}_{+\Phi} \ \mathbf{V}_{-\Phi}]$ (both positive $\mathbf{V}_{+\Phi}$ and negative $\mathbf{V}_{-\Phi}$) and all the nonzero eigenvalues $\mathbf{\Lambda}_\Phi = [\mathbf{\Lambda}_{+\Phi} \ \mathbf{\Lambda}_{-\Phi}]^T$ (both positive $\mathbf{\Lambda}_{+\Phi}$ and negative $\mathbf{\Lambda}_{-\Phi}$) which satisfy $\mathbf{\Lambda}_\Phi \mathbf{V}_\Phi = \mathbf{R}_\Phi \mathbf{V}_\Phi$. Each eigenvector \mathbf{v}_Φ^k in the feature space can be written as a linear combination of the centered input data as $\mathbf{v}_\Phi^k = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N_{in}}} \Phi(\mathbf{X}) \boldsymbol{\alpha}^k \mathbf{\Lambda}_{+\Phi}^{-\frac{1}{2}} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{N_{out}}} \Phi(\mathbf{Y}) \boldsymbol{\beta}^k \mathbf{\Lambda}_{-\Phi}^{-\frac{1}{2}}$, where the expansion coefficients, $\boldsymbol{\alpha}^k$ and $\boldsymbol{\beta}^k$, are defined as $\boldsymbol{\alpha}^k = (\alpha_1^k, \alpha_2^k, \dots, \alpha_{N_{in}}^k)^T$ and $\boldsymbol{\beta}^k = (\beta_1^k, \beta_2^k, \dots, \beta_{N_{out}}^k)^T$ for $k = 1, \dots, N_t$ where $N_t = N_{in} + N_{out}$. In [5] it has been shown that each concatenated expansion coefficients $\mathbf{d}_k = [\boldsymbol{\alpha}^k \ \boldsymbol{\beta}^k]^T$ for $k = 1, \dots, N_t$ is an eigenvector of the KEST kernel matrix

$$\mathbf{K}_{KEST} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\mathbf{K}_{XX}}{N_{in}} & -\frac{\mathbf{K}_{XY}}{N_{in}} \\ \frac{\mathbf{K}_{YX}}{N_{out}} & -\frac{\mathbf{K}_{YY}}{N_{out}} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (13)$$

where $\mathbf{K}_{XX} = \Phi(\mathbf{X})^T \Phi(\mathbf{X})$ is an $N_{in} \times N_{in}$ kernel matrix, $\mathbf{K}_{YY} = \Phi(\mathbf{Y})^T \Phi(\mathbf{Y})$ is an $N_{out} \times N_{out}$ kernel matrix, $\mathbf{K}_{XY} = \Phi(\mathbf{X})^T \Phi(\mathbf{Y})$ is an $N_{in} \times N_{out}$ kernel matrix, and $\mathbf{K}_{YX} = \Phi(\mathbf{Y})^T \Phi(\mathbf{X})$ is an $N_{out} \times N_{in}$ kernel matrix.

By letting the KEST projection vectors, $\mathbf{D}_{KEST} = [\tilde{\mathbf{d}}_1 \ \tilde{\mathbf{d}}_2 \ \cdots \ \tilde{\mathbf{d}}_m]$ be either the first m positive or negative eigenvectors of (13) normalized by the square roots of their corresponding eigenvalues then kernel EST subspace detection, as shown in [5], is given by

$$\text{KEST}(\mathbf{r}) = \left(\mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{Z}_r}^T - \mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{Z}_\mu}^T \right)^T \mathbf{D}_{KEST} \mathbf{D}_{KEST}^T \left(\mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{Z}_r}^T - \mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{Z}_\mu}^T \right) \quad (14)$$

where $\Phi(\mathbf{r})^T \Phi(\mathbf{Z}) = \mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{Z}_r}$ and $\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{\mathbf{Y}_\Phi}^T \Phi(\mathbf{Z}) = \mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{Z}_\mu}$, respectively.

5. RX AND KERNEL-RX ANOMALY DETECTORS

The RX-algorithm [2] is based on comparing the difference between the test spectrum and the spectra of the immediate background samples. It is similar to the Mahalanobis distance measure and is given by

$$\text{RX}(\mathbf{r}) = (\mathbf{r} - \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_Y)^T \mathbf{C}_Y^{-1} (\mathbf{r} - \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_Y), \quad (15)$$

where \mathbf{r} is the test sample, $\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_Y$ and \mathbf{C}_Y are the spectral mean and covariance of the OWR. The RX algorithm can also be considered as a subspace projection-based anomaly detector. Rewriting (15) in terms of its eigen-value decomposition $\mathbf{C}_Y^{-1} = \mathbf{V} \boldsymbol{\Lambda}^{-1} \mathbf{V}^T = \hat{\mathbf{V}} \hat{\mathbf{V}}^T$, where $\hat{\mathbf{V}} = \mathbf{V} \boldsymbol{\Lambda}^{-1/2}$ are considered as the projection vectors, and substituting this result into (15) we obtain the RX algorithm in terms of the projection vectors as

$$\text{RX}(\mathbf{r}) = (\mathbf{r} - \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_Y)^T \hat{\mathbf{V}} \hat{\mathbf{V}}^T (\mathbf{r} - \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_Y). \quad (16)$$

The kernel version of the RX algorithm was obtained in [6] and is given as

$$\text{KRX}(\mathbf{r}) = \left(\mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{Y}_r}^T - \mathbf{K}_{\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_Y}^T \right)^T \hat{\mathbf{K}}_Y^{-1} \left(\mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{Y}_r}^T - \mathbf{K}_{\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_Y}^T \right), \quad (17)$$

where $\mathbf{K}_{\mathbf{Y}_r} = \Phi(\mathbf{r})^T \mathbf{Y}_{c_\Phi}$, $\mathbf{K}_{\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_Y} = \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{\mathbf{Y}_\Phi}^T \mathbf{Y}_{c_\Phi}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{K}}_Y$ is the estimated centered kernel matrix.

6. RESULTS

Each of the anomaly detector is implemented here as a discrimination method on several hyperspectral images. The images that are used are from the Hyperspectral Digital Imagery Collection Experiment (HYDICE). Fig. 1(a) shows one of the spectral band in the Forest Radiance (FR) image data collection which consists of 150 spectral bands ($0.4 - 2.5 \mu\text{m}$) has 14 ‘targets of interest’ in a grassy field situated near a densely wooded area. The ground truth for the FR-I HYDICE image is shown in Fig. 1(b). It clearly shows the location of the fourteen ‘targets of interest’. All eight algorithms were implemented for this image and the outputs for each approach can be seen in Figs. 1(c) - 1(j). The ROC curves for each of the eight algorithms at low FAR are shown in Fig. 2. The results form ROC curves indicate that each of the nonlinear algorithms performs better when compared with its respective linear version.

7. CONCLUSIONS

This paper provides a performance characterization of nonlinear kernel-based methods for hyperspectral anomaly detection. Four linear algorithms are used to generate projection vectors onto which samples from the inner window region and outer window region of a dual window centered at the test pixel are projected. Each of these algorithms is then mapped into a high-dimensional feature space in an attempt to exploit the higher-order correlation between the spectral characteristics of the pixels. The nonlinear algorithms in the feature space are then rewritten in terms of kernels function of the data in the original input space. All eight anomaly detection algorithms are briefly explained and implemented real hyperspectral data cubes.

8. REFERENCES

- [1] D. W. J. Stein, S. G. Beaven, L. E. Hoff, E. M. Winter, A. P. Schaum, and A. D. Stocker, “Anomaly detection from hyperspectral imagery,” *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 58–69, Jan. 2002.
- [2] I. S. Reed and X. Yu, “Adaptive multiple-band cfar detection of an optical pattern with unknown spectral distribution,” *IEEE Trans. Acoust. Speech Signal Process.*, vol. 38, no. 10, pp. 1760–1770, (Oct. 1990).
- [3] B. Scholkopf and A. J. Smola, *Learning with Kernels*, MIT Press, Cambridge, MA, (2002).
- [4] D. Torrieri, “The eigenspace transform for neural network classifiers,” *Neural Networks*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 419–427, April 1999.
- [5] H. Goldberg, H. Kwon, and N. M. Nasrabadi, “Kernel eigenspace separation transform for subspace anomaly detection in hyperspectral imagery,” *IEEE Geoscience and*

Remote Sensing Letters, vol. 4, no. 4, pp. 581–585, Oct. 2007.

- [6] H. Kwon and N. M. Nasrabadi, “Kernel RX-algorithm: A nonlinear anomaly detector for hyperspectral imagery,” *IEEE Trans. on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, vol. 43, no. 2, pp. 388–397, Feb. 2005.

Fig. 1. (a) Original FR-I HYDICE image. (b) Ground truth for the FR-I HYDICE image. Output results at 80% detection rate using (c) RX, (d) PCA, (e) FLD, (f) EST, (g) KRX, (h) KPCA, (i) KFD, and (j) KEST.

Fig. 2. ROC curves obtained from all the eight techniques for the FR Image at low false alarm rates.